

École Pratique des Hautes Études
Sciences de la vie et de la terre

PhD proposal for Indonesian Student (LDPD PhD program)

Name and position of thesis supervisor:

Prof. Dr. Thierry Wirth, Director of Studies (Ex. class) at the EPHE
Tel: 01 40 79 80 36 Email: wirth@mnhn.fr

Name of research unit affiliated to the EPHE hosting the doctoral student:

Phyloepidemiology and Phylodynamics of Pathogens (PHYLOPATH), UMR-CNRS 7205, ISYEB, 16 rue Buffon, Paris, France.

Name of research unit Director: Prof. Dr. Violaine Colin

École Doctorale numéro 472 de l'École Pratique des Hautes Études

International co-supervision of thesis envisaged: Yes, a co-supervision could be envisioned but not mandatory.

Laboratory description:

The ISYEB PHYLOPATH team is led by Prof. Dr. Thierry Wirth, he is also holding a Leibniz Leibniz Chair at the Lung Centrum in Germany, Borstel. In terms of permanent members, the team is made up of three professors, two senior lecturers, one engineer and one technician. The team has privileged access to the Natural History Museum computer cluster and several Mac Pros with 1TB of RAM, providing an excellent working environment for the candidate, particularly for bioinformatics and genomic analyses.

Financial resources for sequencing are available thanks to funding gleaned from two ANR projects (TB-Emerg and ResToITB).

Thesis Project

Title: Integrative approaches to combat the tuberculosis epidemic in Indonesia

Context and problematic:

Most of the people who develop TB disease each year are in 30 high TB burden countries, which accounted for 87% of the global total in 2023. Among them, Indonesia represents the second largest fraction (10%). However, the most worrying situation is due to the increase in multi-drug resistant and rifampicin resistant (MDR, RR-TB) strains. More than 400,000 people are currently developing **MDR/RR-TB**, leading to increased costs and treatment failures, and Indonesia is once again at the forefront. Furthermore, among the three global lists of **high-burden countries** for TB, HIV-associated TB and MDR/RR-TB being used by WHO in the period 2021–2025, **Indonesia** appears on all of them. The likelihood of developing the disease is greater in groups affected by risk factors such as alcoholism, smoking, diabetes, malnutrition and HIV infection¹. Social status also appears to play a significant role. Despite a steady decline in the number of new cases reported since the beginning of the century, the spread of drug-resistant strains now poses a significant risk of a pandemic^{1,2}.

The work of Thierry Wirth's team focuses in particular on an evolutionary line of the *M. tuberculosis* complex enriched with multi-resistant strains. This is **lineage 2**, known as "**Beijing**", which is enjoying unprecedented worldwide success². In the current context of intense population movements, often linked to economical and conflict-related migrations, understanding the biological, macro-economic and social factors influencing the expansion of such clades is a fundamental step towards establishing effective **health policies**. To this end, the proposed thesis project is divided into three parts, presented below, each addressing, at different scales, the influence of **migration policies** on the spread and epidemic success of antibiotic-resistant strains of *M. tuberculosis* in Indonesia.

Objectives and hypotheses

We will begin by looking at the emergence and spread of multi-drug-resistant strains in the Indonesian Archipelago among groups of individuals who have immigrated from different countries with a high incidence of tuberculosis. Indonesia is a host territory for many refugees and economic immigrants. This makes it a particularly interesting area to study in the context of understanding the consequences of **migratory flows**¹⁰ and **reception policies** in the South-Pacific. The aim of this part of the project will be to compare the spread of resistant strains and the epidemic success of *M. tuberculosis* in countries with different migration and **integration policies**, on the assumption that these influence certain epidemic parameters. Studies focusing more on the human and social sciences and the links between health and migration have already highlighted the impact of reception and information policies on the risk of tuberculosis among immigrant populations. The lack of awareness and testing prior to departure, the difficulty of integration and access to skilled jobs once in the host country are all factors that make certain populations all the more vulnerable to the disease. It is therefore essential to be able to adapt the reception and management of migratory flows as much as possible.

Secondly, there is accumulating evidence that the China-Papua New-Guinea trade is contributing to the spread of multi-resistant strains from the Beijing lineage to East Papua¹². Papua and more specifically its high plains, is one of the last regions on the planet where Western civilisation arrived just over a century ago. Paradoxically, this country is now one of those where tuberculosis is most prevalent in the world, with more than 30,000 new cases each year and more than 3,000 deaths. This lineage is thought to have appeared nearly 8,000 years ago in the Yangtze basin³. From this initial focus, the Beijing lineage gradually spread around the world, following the main trade routes. The ongoing trade led to the arrival of Chinese workers and engineers in East-Papua, particularly in the construction and mining sectors. It is therefore particularly interesting to **compare the situation in Indonesian West Papua** in terms of the prevalence of MDR strains, which is involved in modest activities linked to China, **with that in West Papua New Guinea**, which is heavily involved.

By adopting a **multidisciplinary** approach on different scales (national, continental and global), it will be possible to better understand how **socio-political dynamics** can impact the evolution of the pathogen responsible for tuberculosis.

Methodology

1) Population genomics and molecular epidemiology

Thanks to a precise estimate of the mutation rates at the genomic level, the effective population sizes of the different evolutionary lineages of tuberculosis can be calculated. This results in contrasting demographic variables and behaviours, which have a direct impact on transmission chains⁴. By generating complete genomes⁵ of strains representative of the main evolutionary lineages of the *M. tuberculosis* complex present in the Indonesian Archipelago, we plan to: i) Link the genetic structuring of *M. tuberculosis* with the recent history of human migrations in the areas concerned (at least the major Islands, i.e. Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Maluku, West Papua). ii) To compare the demography of the different *M. tuberculosis* evolutionary lineages, as well as that of multi-drug resistant (MDR-TB) and ultra-drug resistant (XDR-TB) strains, with that of susceptible strains (estimation of the relative success of the lineages). iii) To link the population genetics of *M. tuberculosis* with different social and economic parameters (immigration, integration policy, incidence in the country of origin, level of qualification, social class, healthcare system, international trade, etc.) in order to identify and model the socio-economic determinants of the dynamics of the spread of the disease⁶.

However, in order to fully understand the evolutionary processes that may explain the epidemic success of the lineages under consideration, including the Beijing lineage, which is widely distributed in Indonesia, it is essential to examine the very notion of epidemic success. In my team, we developed algorithms and analysis tools that enable the epidemiological success of a strain to be objectively and mathematically quantified based on genotypic data. The success of a group of bacteria is proportional to the frequency associated with its transmission event over a period⁷⁻⁹. Based on this assumption, measuring the density associated with an isolate's haplotype (THD - Timescaled Haplotypic Densities) reflects the epidemic success of its ancestors. The use of THD will make it possible to take joint account of the epidemiological, clinical and genetic data available to us⁷.

Finally, by analysing genomic data using Bayesian approaches, it will be possible to reconstruct phylogenetic trees showing transmission chains between strains in the same epidemic phase⁴. This tool can also be used to reconstruct demographic changes in a bacterial population and to map the order of appearance of resistance mutations on the topology of the tree. Finally, we are also able to calculate branch-by-branch substitution rates. Using Bayesian phylogeny tools, we will be able to study the characteristics of the **dominant strains**, as well as their **demogenetic evolution** within the groups considered.

2) In silico antibiotic profiling

As already exemplified, the results from whole-genome sequencing of TB clinical sample in Papua, Indonesia, could contribute to the surveillance of TB-drug resistance. In a pilot study in silico drug resistance profiles were successfully obtained for 15 Multi Drugs Resistance (MDR) samples¹¹. Our goal, as partners of the French and German reference centres of tuberculosis is to **democratize WGS-based antibiotic profiling in Indonesia** which is still in its infancy by implementing MTB-seq and home-made script to **accelerate the diagnostic and reduce the risks of fall positives**.

3) Economic epidemiology and multivariate analyses

In order to carry out the project presented, it will be essential to draw on data and knowledge concerning both the macro-economic phenomena mentioned above and the migration policies of the countries studied. This project aims to promote trans-disciplinarity between evolutionary genomics and the human sciences, drawing on economics, sociology, geography and history. In this context, work on the concepts of economic epidemiology or the more general link between health and migration are bibliographic starting points for our work. They also seek to highlight the consequences of such mobility and to draw up recommendations for economic, national and international policies, particularly in terms of health.

Economic epidemiology places disease and preventive/curative behaviour at the centre of the analysis and leads to so-called 'prevalence-elastic' behaviour. This literature is based on the rational choice hypothesis used in classical microeconomics, applied here to healthcare choices. These expected utility models differ from ordinary epidemiological models in that they incorporate the preventive behaviour of individuals in response to disease dynamics. This behaviour in turn influences the transmission of the disease. The epidemiological characteristics of a disease linked to human behaviour can lead to possible health traps¹⁶. In other words, the externalities (unexpected effects) linked to the supposedly rational preventive behaviour of individuals may lead the group to remain 'trapped' in a stable and high level of disease transmission. Nevertheless, the analysis of a disease cannot be limited to a theoretical view of behaviour.

This analysis must be compared with empirical data. DHS or more macroeconomic data could be combined with genomic data. In addition, the determinants of a disease in an economic system and the impact of this disease on trade flows, productivity and even education are intimately linked. The impact of a disease on development and economic growth is endogenous to this evolutionary system.

Expected results

In terms of results, we expect to collect and sequence nearly 600 strains from the main islands that belong to the Indonesian Archipelago. We expect there to be few hurdles to overcome in terms of genotyping (funding for analyses is guaranteed via the ANR). From the raw data we will be able to reconstruct the demographic history of lineages, generate phylogenies as well as minimum spanning trees and transmission chains between individuals. Epidemicity indices (THD) will be calculated on our computer clusters using our own scripts.

With regard to ancillary data and economic and social indices, a great deal of work will be required at the start of the thesis to collect patients' socio-demographic data. This data will be digitised and formatted so that it can be used in multivariate analyses (PCA, MDS, GWAS). Secondly, the student will collect and cross-reference macroeconomic and migratory data relating to South-Pacific region, as well as to the China-Papua issue. The third stage will involve combining molecular and genomic epidemiological data with epidemiological data relating to the sociology of individuals. On a broader scale, this work will also cover migration and economic aspects.

Provisional timetable

Year 1:

- Genomics and typing: Construction of databases, entry of data already acquired (Genomes). Initiation of NGS sequencing (Illumina) of Indonesian strains, assembly.
- Ancillary data: Acquisition and formatting of patient socio-demographic data. Acquisition of macroeconomic and migratory data for target regions and countries.

Year 2:

- Bioinformatics analyses: Demogenetic reconstructions with BEAST, phylogenetic analyses (PhyML, PastML), network and transmission chains (MSTree), epidemicity calculations (THD), GWAS on quantitative traits (transmissibility, socio-economic indices).
- Multivariate analyses combining genetic data with economic, migratory and socio-demographic data (PCA, MDS, etc.).

Year 3:

- First semester: Drafting of paper N°1: Effects of migratory and economic flows on the diversity of the Beijing lineage in Indonesia.
- Second semester: Drafting of paper N°2: Effects of migration policies on the epidemicity and transmissibility of *M. tuberculosis* strains in Indonesia.

Year 4:

- First semester: Drafting of paper N°3: Quantification of the socio-demographic effects of patients on transmission chains and on the epidemicity of associated strains.
- Second semester: Compilation of publications and drafting of the thesis.

Desired profile: We are looking for a student with a particular interest in genomics, informatics and multidisciplinary.

References

1. Global tuberculosis report 2024. Genève : World Health Organization; (2024).
2. Merker, M. et al. Evolutionary history and global spread of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis Beijing lineage. *Nat. Genet.* 47, 242–249 (2015).
3. Comas, I. et al. Out-of-Africa migration and Neolithic coexpansion of Mycobacterium tuberculosis with modern humans. *Nat. Genet.* 45, 1176–1182 (2013).
4. Wirth, T. et al. Origin, Spread and Demography of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis Complex. *PLoS Pathog.* 4, e1000160 (2008).
5. Roetzer, A. et al. Whole Genome Sequencing versus Traditional Genotyping for Investigation of a Mycobacterium tuberculosis Outbreak: A Longitudinal Molecular Epidemiological Study. *PLOS Med.* 10, e1001387 (2013).
6. Berthélemy, J.-C., Thuilliez, J., Doumbo, O. & Gaudart, J. Malaria and protective behaviours: is there a malaria trap? *Malar. J.* 12, 200 (2013).
7. Rasigade, J.-P. et al. Strain-specific estimation of epidemic success provides insights into the transmission dynamics of tuberculosis. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 45326 (2017).
8. Wirth, T. Massive lineage replacements and cryptic outbreaks of Salmonella Typhi in eastern and southern Africa. *Nat. Genet.* 47, 565–567 (2015).
9. Barbier, M. et al. Changing patterns of human migrations shaped the global population structure of Mycobacterium tuberculosis in France. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 5855 (2018).
10. Bainomugisa A. et al. Cross-Border Movement of Highly Drug-Resistant Mycobacterium tuberculosis from Papua New Guinea to Australia through Torres Strait Protected Zone, 2010–2015. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 25, 406-415 (2019).
11. Maladan et al. The whole-genome sequencing in predicting Mycobacterium tuberculosis drug susceptibility and resistance in Papua, Indonesia. *BMC Genomics* 22:844 (2021).
12. Bainomugisa A et al. Evolution and spread of a highly drug-resistant strain of Mycobacterium tuberculosis in Papua New Guinea. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 22:437 (2022).

Curriculum vitae

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Date of birth: 8th of August 1966 (in Mulhouse, France)
Nationality: French
Family situation: divorced, 1 child
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EMPLOYMENT HISTORY

Accreditation to direct Research (HDR), University Paris-Sud XI, UFR Scientifique d'Orsay (2006).

2023-2028: EPHE vice-president in charge of International Relations
2006–present Full Professor EPHE/Museum of Natural History, Paris
2004-2006 Assistant Professor at Konstanz University (Chair of Zoology and Evolution).
2000-2004 Postdoctoral fellow at the Max-Planck Institute for Infectious Diseases, Berlin, Germany
1998-2000 Postdoctoral fellow at the University Laval, Québec, Canada
1994-1998 PhD at the University Basel, Switzerland.

HONORS

2022-2026: Leibniz Chair holder at the Leibniz Science Campus of Evolutionary Medicine of the Lung Borstel, Germany
2025: Invited Professor at the Department of Immunology and Infectious Diseases Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health (Prof. Sarah Fortune).
2016: William H. Telfer Endowed Lectureship at the Pennsylvania University, USA

FIELD OF STUDY

Researcher and Professor in evolutionary genomics, I investigate the evolutionary history, dispersion, and molecular epidemiology of major human pathogens. My research integrates population genomics, Bayesian statistics, machine learning approaches, and Approximate Bayesian Computation (ABC) to study epidemic dynamics, the emergence of antibiotic resistance, and secondary compensatory mutations in multidrug-resistant strains. Through sustained international and national collaborations with the Institut Pasteur, Pitié-Salpêtrière Hospital, Robert Koch Institute, Statens Serum Institut, Max-Planck Institute, and other leading institutions in Germany, Denmark, and the United States, I focus on key pathogens such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Yersinia pestis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Helicobacter pylori*, and respiratory viruses. These studies explore the coalescent history, demography, origins, and the impact of human migrations and globalisation on pathogen dissemination.

Domains of expertise: Evolutionary Biology, Microbiology, Population Genomics, Molecular Epidemiology, ABC Computation, Spatio-temporal Modelling, Environmental Metagenomics, and Signatures of Selection.

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

Plague (*Yersinia pestis*): Co-initiated in 2003 with Mark Achtman an ambitious international project to sequence ~100 global strains. This collaborative effort led to a landmark publication in *Nature Genetics* (2010) and generated significant media coverage, including France 5, France Culture, Le Monde, Libération, and Le Nouvel Observateur.

Tuberculosis (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*): Reconstructed the evolutionary history of the tubercle bacillus in a 2008 *PLoS Pathogens* paper (335 citations, top 20 in the field), prompting a joint MNHN/CNRS press release. Contributed to a highly cited *PLoS Medicine* article (2013, 392 citations) demonstrating the power of genomic epidemiology for outbreak tracing and source identification. As last author, published a key *Nature Genetics* study (2015, 417 citations) on the Beijing lineage, identifying genes under diversifying selection with direct implications for MDR-TB diagnostics.

Helicobacter pylori: I was a post-doc in the team of Mark Achtman when we were able to show that the gut bacteria, *H. pylori*, was a perfect tool to trace back human population movements and to detect introgression signatures. This work was published in *Science* (2003, 772 citations) and *PNAS* (2004, 127 citations).

Escherichia coli: As first author, demonstrated the link between bacterial sex and virulence in a 2006 *Molecular Microbiology* paper (>1,700 citations, among the top 20,000 most cited articles ever). This study introduced a new paradigm for the emergence of pathogenic strains and has since been confirmed across multiple bacterial species.

AWARDS & GRANTS

- Swiss National Fonds support (120 k€); CRSNG/FCAR, Canada (180 k€); German DFG (100 k€); ATM Muséum “Biodiversity and role of micro-organisms in past and present ecosystems” (420 k€), ANR IM-model@coralfish (135 k€); EUROPE-ASPIRE, Pfizer company (50 k€); GENOSCOPE, project Evo-metagenomics (100 k€); ANR TB-EMERGE (600 k€); ANR RESISTRACK (620 k€), ANR SAHYLOR (447 k€), ANR RESTOL-TB (714 k€), Grant TYPHI-TRACL (240 k€).

PUBLICATIONS & BOOK CHAPTERS

- 85 publications, 10 book chapters and participation to 64 international conferences (invited 41 times). Hirsch = 47 in Google Scholar; ISI WEB of KNOWLEDGE citation index = 8,061. Average citation per item > 100 times, mean impact factor >10. WOS identifier: B-4915-2008

SCIENTIFIC and ADMINISTRATIVE RESPONSABILITIES

- Member of the Board of Directors of Université PSL, 2022-2025
- Member of the scientific council of Paris Sciences et Lettres (PSL) – 2016/2020
- Member of the scientific council at the Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes – 2018/2025
- Member of the Board of Directors (EPHE) – 2014/2017 and 2026/2030
- Head of the “Speciation and Systematics” department at the Natural History Museum (UMR 7205) – 2015/2018
- Editor for *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*, 2016 – 2020
- Referee for > 20 different scientific journals (including *Science, Nature, Nature Genetics, Nature Microbiology, Nature Communications, The Lancet Microbe...*)
- External expert of the European Union, the Institut Pasteur (France); the Agropolis Foundation; the French Research Agency ANR; the French HCERES; the Netherland Genomics Initiative; the Central Finance and Contracting Agency (CFCA) of the Republic of Latvia; the National Centre of Science and Technology Evaluation Republic of Kazakhstan; the ESCMID Study Group Research Grants ; the Medical Research Council (UK); member of the Scientific Committee of the 14th International Conference on Molecular Epidemiology and Evolutionary Genetics of Infectious Diseases MEEEGID XIV, Sitges, Spain; member of the scientific committee for the international conference on the Evolution and Paleoepidemiology of Tuberculosis, Szeged, Hungary; member of the scientific committee for the Union World Conference of Lung Health, Copenhagen, Denmark,

MISCELLANEOUS

- Publications on tuberculosis and plague were covered by different media: Le Point, Le Nouvel Observateur, Le Monde, Libération, France Culture, le Magazine de la Santé (TV5), the New-York Times, the Scientist, Nature News, Research Highlight Nature and the New-Scientist.
- Military Service at the Louis Pasteur Hospital (CHA) in Berlin, Germany, 1990-1991.

TEN SIGNIFICANT PUBLICATIONS

- Barilar I, Fernando T, Utpatel C, Abujate C, Madeira CM, José B, Mutaquiha C, Kranzer K, Niemann T, Ismael N, de Araujo L, Wirth T, Niemann S, Viegas S (2024). Emergence of bedaquiline-resistant tuberculosis and of multidrug-resistant and extensively drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains with rpoB lle491Phe mutation not detected by Xpert MTB/RIF in Mozambique: a retrospective observational study. *Lancet Infectious Diseases* 23: 297-307. IF = 31.0
- Merker M, Rasigade JP, Barbier M, Cox H, Feuerriegel S, Kohl TA, Shitikov E, Klaos K, Gaudin C, Antoine R, Diel R, Borrell S, Gagneux S, Nikolayevskyy V, Andres S, Crudu V, Supply P, Niemann S, Wirth T (2022). Transcontinental spread and evolution of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* W148 European/Russian clade toward extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis. *Nature Communications*, 15: 5105. IF = 15.7
- Dreyer V, Mandal A, Dev P, Merker M, Barilar I, Utpatel C, Nilgiriwala K, Rodrigues C, Crook DW, Rasigade JP, Wirth T, Mistry N, Niemann S (2022). High fluoroquinolone resistance proportions among multidrug-resistant tuberculosis driven by dominant L2 *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* clones in the Mumbai Metropolitan Region. *Genome Medicine*, 14: 1-16. IF = 11,2.
- Wirth T (2021). When specialized clones go global. *Nature Microbiology*, 6: 1215-1216. IF = 19.4
- Wirth T, Bergot M, Rasigade JP, Pichon B, Barbier M, Martins-Simoes P, Jacob L, Pike R, Tissieres P, Picaud JC, Kearns A, Supply P, Butin M, Laurent F (2020). Niche specialization and spread of a *Staphylococcus capitis* clone involved in neonatal sepsis. *Nature Microbiology*, 5: 735-745. IF = 19.4
- Wirth T (2015) Massive lineage replacements and cryptic outbreaks of *Salmonella* Typhi in eastern and southern Africa. *Nature Genetics* 47: 565-567. IF = 29.0
- Merker M, Blin C, Mona S, Duforet-Freboung N, Lecher S, Willery E, Blum M, Rüsche-Gerdes S, Mokrousov I, Aleksic E, Nikolayevskyy V, Rasmussen M, Rastogi N, Samper S, Sanchez-Padilla E, Savic B, Chola Shamputa I, Shen A, Sng LH, Stakenas P, Toit T, Varaine F, Vukovic D, Wahl C, Warren R, Supply P, Niemann S & Wirth T (2015). Evolutionary history and global spread of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Beijing lineage. *Nature Genetics* 47: 242-249. IF = 29.0
- Wirth T., Wang X., Linz B. et al. (2004) Distinguishing human ethnic groups by means of sequences from *Helicobacter pylori*: Lessons from Ladakh. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 101: 4746-4751. IF = 8.9
- Falush D., Wirth, T., Linz B. et al (2003) Traces of human migration in *Helicobacter pylori*. *Science* 299: 1582-1585. IF = 45.8
- Wirth T & Bernatchez L (2001). Genetic evidence against panmixia in the European eel. *Nature* 409: 1037-1040. IF = 48.5

THREE SIGNIFICANT BOOK CHAPTERS

- Gharbi N, Rousseau E & Wirth T “Clock rates and Bayesian evaluation of temporal signal” in *Phylogenomics: Foundations, Methods, and Pathogen Analysis* – Academic Press (2024).
- Barbier M & Wirth T “The evolutionary history, demography and spread of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC)” in *Tuberculosis and the Tubercle Bacillus*, 2nd Edition, American Society for Microbiology Press (2018).
- Gilabert A & Wirth T “Elucidating human migration by means of their pathogens” in *Genetics and Evolution of Infectious Diseases*, Edited by Michel Tybarenc, Elsevier (2011).

